

ADVERSE EFFECTS OF ALCOHOL CONSUMPTION AND ITS IMPACT ON SOCIETY IN TAMILNADU

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Abstract:

The study, explains that the alcohol consumption increases the health problems and risks; most of the young drinkers were injured due to accident as well as they face health problems related to alcohol. Therefore, there are likely chances to reduce the mental ability, reducing self-confident due alcoholism and increasing trend among youth. The study also confirmed that the living conditions, economic level, consumption of alcohol and intake of non-vegetable food, snacks during drinking create stomach pain and ulcer.

Key Words: Alcoholism, Alcohol Consumption & Health Problems

Alcoholism:

Day by day alcohol is becoming increasingly available and is used widely. Addiction has become really a curse upon human beings. It affects not only the alcoholics but also others directly or indirectly. For common people it is a weakness of character. A moral theologian may see it as a matter of vice while sociologists see it as a social problem. It is considered a sin by religious people and as a crime by law enforcement groups. The psychiatrist can describe it as a personality disorder problem. The alcoholics' anonymous groups and the treatment centres call them patients and alcoholism is handled as a disease.

Impact of Alcoholism:

More males are affected by alcoholism than females. Recent surveys show that drinking is increasing among the youth and women. Consumption of alcohol is apparently on the rise over the world. The total alcohol consumption and prevalence of alcohol-related problems are high in all the societies, especially in societies of developing nations. Initially, the alcoholics may demonstrate a high tolerance to alcohol, consuming more and showing fewer adverse effects than others. Subsequently, however, the person begins to drink against his or her own best interests, as alcohol comes to assume more importance than personal relationships, work, reputation, or even physical health. The person commonly loses control over drinking and is increasingly unable to predict how much alcohol will be consumed on a given occasion or, if the person is currently abstaining or when the drinking will resume again. Physical dependency leads one to have withdrawal symptoms when sufficient drink is not available.

Alcohol in India:

In general the common opinion in India about taking alcohol is that it is evil to do so. There is no acceptance of drinking alcohol in a social manner or as stimulant – so you cannot find openness towards the consumption of alcohol in any form. In the common opinion taking alcohol in any amount is proscribed, especially in some form of religions and for women. Anyhow making a taboo out of drinking alcohol does not solve the problem at all. It rather makes it more tempting. In addition to that most of all the alcohol regulation policies formed by each state are unsuccessful and since it is a taboo topic there is not enough information provided. Due to the fact that alcohol selling in many states is controlled by the government there are many adulteration of alcohol and a black market occurred.

Furthermore alcohol consumption is also a big problem in rural areas. Most of the rural populations work in the sector of manual labour. They suffer from the hard work and by drinking alcohol after work they try to suppress the pain to be able to go to work the next day. That is a very common way of getting into the vicious circle.

Alcohol Policy in Tamilnadu:

Alcohol in Tamil Nadu is sold only by "TASMAC" (Tamil Nadu State Marketing Corporation), a company holds by the government of Tamil Nadu. Within the last years all private shops which sold alcohol were shut down. With 50 % of the total amount the taxes on alcohol in Tamil Nadu are very high. The government can finally record most of the taxes revenue as a profit since it has the monopoly on selling. In total nearly half of the annual tax receipts are taken by the revenue from alcohol. Anyhow all of this has led to corruption in retail outlets and many complaints.

The place for TASMAC bars has to follow specific guidelines and norms as for example prescribed distance to school, places of worship etc. Anyhow many of the TASMAC bars don't meet those standards. In Coimbatore many people feel disturbed by the drunker near to their house as well as it is a danger for people to start drinking alcohol at all. Without the availability of alcohol people would not have the chance to get in anyhow. Within the last year many people petitioned for a shifting or a closing of those shops. And they have been successful: In 2012, 14 TASMAC outlets in Coimbatore District were shifted.

Anyhow in many places TASMAC outlets still allow the alcoholics to have easy access to all kinds of liquids. Getting all the tax revenues the Tamil Nadu government is not willing to arrange those necessary shifting.

Objectives of the Study:

The overall objective of the study is to identify reasons for the increasing trend of alcohol consumption in Tamil Nadu and its multitude impact on society.

The secondary objective of the study is to find out Social, Economic and Behavioural Problems Caused by Alcohol Abuse.

Significance of the Study:

In India, the problem of alcohol abuse has become a matter of serious public concern, especially on account of its proliferation among the youth in various socio-cultural and economic statuses. Although there are no definite figures to show the actual extent of the problem, yet the rising number of alcohol abuse approaching the drug counseling and de addiction centers indicates the increasing magnitude and extent of the problem. Alcohol abuse is the burning issue and an important area of research at the moment, it is also the one area which it ignored, and may lead to serious unfavorable and undesirable may disastrous consequences particularly for our younger generation.

Most of the earlier researches seem to be directed towards students, Major loss of income and psychiatric patients, general population. But none of the study has been conducted to the personality of alcohol abusers in relation to socio-economic status. There for the basis of above views the following problem is selected for the research purpose. "Adverse effects of the increasing trend of alcohol consumption and its impact on society: a study in in Tamil Nadu" which are very much associated with alcohol abuse and personality.

Related Studies:

Sher et al (1991) explains that the personality variables have been viewed as having only indirect effects on disorders; that is their primary effects are mediated by other variables more proximal to outcome. It has been posited that individuals who are

high on trait related to negative affectivity are more likely to experience subjective distress and consequently turn to alcohol for 'self-medication' purposes. Sher *et al* suggested that the effect of family history on offspring alcoholism could be mediated by such a multistage chain where family history (a distal variable) is related to behavioral under control (a personality variable) which in turn is related to alcohol outcome expectancies (a proximal variable) which in turn is related to alcohol involvement.

Subirkumar Das, V. Balakrishnan, D. M. Vasudevan (2002) suggested alcoholic beverages have been used in human societies since the beginning of recorded history. The patterns of alcohol intake around the world are constantly evolving, and alcohol is ubiquitous today. Research has contributed substantially to our understanding of the relation of drinking to specific disorders, and has shown that the relation between alcohol consumption and health outcomes is complex and multidimensional. Increases in the average volume of drinking are predicted for the most populous regions of the world in Southeast Asia including India. Cultural differences apparently influence the pattern of alcohol consumption. In addition, alcohol is linked to categories of disease whose relative impact on the global burden is predicted to increase. Therefore, it is appropriate to implement policies with targeted harm reduction strategies. The crucial need, from a public health perspective, is for regular means of coordination whereby prevention of alcohol-related problems is taken fully into account in policy decisions about alcohol control and regulation in the market for alcoholic beverages.

Douglas Murdoch and Deborah Ross (1990) point out that Current issue in alcohol-related violence are highlighted through the examination of correlation studies between alcohol and violent crime. Alcohol is associated with violent crime at a greater than chance level and at a significantly higher level than it is associated with nonviolent crime. Heavy drinking and a verbal argument usually precede the violent act and the victim is as likely as the offender to initiate the altercation. However, it is the precipitator of the altercation who is more likely to be intoxicated. Alcohol and aggression are more strongly related than expected with violent offenders demonstrating psychopathology. Marital violence appears related to alcohol independent of other marital problems. Although there exists a strong correlation relationship between alcohol and violent crime, the nature of the evidence prohibits the establishment of a causal link. In particular, methodological problems, such as a lack of appropriate comparison groups, make it difficult to draw conclusions in this area.

Data Analysis:

Table 1: Screening Test (CAGE) of the Respondents

S.No	CAGE	Yes	%	No	%
1.	Have you ever felt you needed to Cut down on your drinking?	84	16.8	41	8.2
2.	Have people Annoyed you by criticizing your drinking?	92	18.4	33	6.6
3.	Have you ever felt Guilty about drinking?	77	15.4	48	9.6
4.	Have you ever felt you needed a drink first thing in the morning (Eye-opener) to steady your nerves or to get rid of a hangover?	88	17.6	37	7.4
	Total	341	68.2	159	31.8

Source: Primary data

The CAGE questionnaire, among other methods, has been extensively validated for use in identifying alcoholism. CAGE is considered a validated screening technique, with one study determining that CAGE test scores ≥ 2 had a specificity of 76% and a

sensitivity of 93% for the identification of excessive drinking and a specificity of 77% and a sensitivity of 91% for the identification of alcoholism.

Most of the respondents 68.2 percent are answered yes. It indicates people are easily addicted alcoholism. So, all the respondents scored more than 2. So, all respondents are consuming alcohol.

Social Problems:

The social problem measures include Change in political beliefs, Change in religious beliefs, Change in social activities, Unemployment, Break up education, Low self-esteem, Tend to feel out of place in society and Incidence of eve-teasing, group clashes.

Table 2: Chi-Square test for Social Problems

	Change in political beliefs	Change in religious beliefs	Change in social activities	Unemployment	Break up education	Low self esteem	Tend to feel out of place in society	Incidence of eve-teasing, group clashes
Chi-Square	269.216 ^a	191.516 ^a	139.772 ^a	197.872 ^a	86.488 ^a	130.532 ^a	168.640 ^a	208.624 ^a
Degrees of Freedom	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5.

b. The minimum expected cell frequency is 71.4.

Source: Output generated from SPSS 21.

From above table, it is found out that all the variables under Social problem measures had a significance value less than 0.05 at 5% level of significance, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus it is concluded that respondents are agreed with Social problem measures in the study unit.

Economic Problems:

The second factor, Major loss of income, Low level of saving habits, Loss of or damage to personal property, Major purchase and Credit difficulties.

Table 3: Chi-Square test for Economic Problems

	Major loss of Income	Low Level of Saving Habits	Loss of or Damage to Personal Property	Major Purchase	Credit Difficulties
Chi-Square	144.840 ^a	102.924 ^a	153.072 ^a	145.988 ^a	253.376 ^b
Degrees of freedom	6	6	6	6	7
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 71.4.

b. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 62.5.

Source: Output generated from SPSS 21.

From the above table, it is found out that all the variables under Economic alcohol abuse problems had a significance value less than 0.05 at 5% level of significance, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus it is concluded that the respondents are agreed with Economic alcohol abuse problems in the study unit.

Behaviour Problems:

The third factor, crying easily, suddenly scared for no reason, I have problems with memory and concentration, Feeling no interest in things, Thoughts of ending your life, and Feeling fearful.

Table 4: Chi-Square test for Behaviour Problems

	Crying easily	Suddenly scared for no reason	I have problems with memory and concentration	Feeling no interest in things	Thoughts of ending my life	Feeling fearful
Chi-Square	190.312 ^a	152.008 ^a	159.568 ^a	166.344 ^a	112.612 ^a	159.008 ^a
Degrees of freedom	6	6	6	6	6	6
Asymp. Sig.	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 71.4.

Source: Output generated from SPSS 21

From the above table, it is found out that all the variables under Behaviour alcohol abuse problems had a significance value less than 0.05 at 5% level of significance, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus it is concluded that respondents are agreed with Behaviour alcohol abuse problems in the study unit..

Findings:

- ✓ Most of the respondents 68.2 percent are answered yes. It indicates people are easily addicted alcoholism. So, all the respondents scored more than 2. So, all respondents are consuming alcohol.
- ✓ All the variables under Economic problems had a significance value less than 0.05 at 5% level of significance, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus it is concluded that the respondents are agreed with Economic problems in the study unit.
- ✓ All the variables under Behaviour problems had a significance value less than 0.05 at 5% level of significance, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus it is concluded that respondents are agreed with Behaviour problems in the study unit
- ✓ All the variables under Social problems had a significance value less than 0.05 at 5% level of significance, thus the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus it is concluded that respondents are agreed with Social problems in the study unit

Suggestions:

In the light of the above, the following suggestions and recommendations are made:

- ✓ Alcohol use is an important public health problem in this area, especially due to the high prevalence rate and a larger involvement of adult age group. Prevalence of alcohol use is high, especially among males. Health educational interventions and proper treatment may help in reducing the burden of alcohol use in this area.
- ✓ Restrictions on the sale of alcohol can be imposed to reduce consumption, if it is impossible to stop. This has to be implemented to its fullest. For instance, decreasing the number of wine shops and/or raising prices of alcohol via taxation will be a right step. Another policy which will improve the health of the people is a ban on alcohol. Thus, wine shops in the rural areas must be permanently closed. However, the implementation of this policy requires much political will on the part of government.
- ✓ Given that persons below the age of 21 are found drinking alcohol, proof of age should be a requirement for the purchase of alcohol. Thus, sales agents must demand age proof from prospective buyers. Such proofs can be done by simply inspecting the identity card of the buyer and such rules must be strictly enforced.

- ✓ Rehabilitation and counseling centers should be established in rural areas to help people who are negatively affected by alcohol and those who wish to quit. The rehabilitation and counseling centers will help bring a health behavioral change among the people and result in improved health.
- ✓ Since the film stars are respected very highly in village areas, their drinking scenes should be avoided as far as possible from films.

Conclusion:

In India recently Alcohol use and abuse is a serious problem among young people. There are a number of unhealthy risks connected with it, including alcohol dependence, and alcohol related accidents and violent behavior. Alcohol dependence is a worldwide problem as its self-induced intoxication is socially tolerable. Alcohol as a disease driving force causes discriminating and chronic intoxication, cirrhosis of liver, toxic psychosis, pancreatitis, and gastritis, cardiac. Also support is mounting that it is correlated to cancers of mouth, pharynx, larynx and esophagus. Alcohol is one of the leading causes of death and disability globally and in India.

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